

/gpm/archive/GPM2220000811.xml: model creation parameters

Analytical parameters: [excel](#)

Parameter	Value
list path, default parameters:	../tandem/methods/qstar.xml
list path, taxonomy information:	../tandem/taxonomy.xml
output, histogram column width:	30
output, histograms:	yes
output, maximum valid expectation value:	0.1
output, maximum valid protein expectation value:	0.1
output, parameters:	yes
output, path:	../gpm/archive/GPM2220000811.xml
output, path hashing:	no
output, performance:	yes
output, proteins:	yes
output, results:	valid
output, sequences:	yes
output, sort results by:	protein
output, spectra:	yes
output, title:	Models from 'Dan-Rif1-IDIRT-1mMXlink-20141120.mzXML'
output, xsl path:	/tandem/tandem-style.xsl
protein, C-terminal residue modification mass:	
protein, N-terminal residue modification mass:	0.0
protein, cleavage C-terminal mass change:	+17.002735
protein, cleavage N-terminal limit:	
protein, cleavage N-terminal mass change:	+1.007825
protein, cleavage semi:	no
protein, cleavage site:	[RK] {P}
protein, quick acetyl:	yes
protein, taxon:	mouse
protein, use annotations:	no
refine:	yes
refine, cleavage semi:	no
refine, maximum valid expectation value:	0.01
refine, point mutations:	no
refine, potential C-terminus modifications:	
refine, potential N-terminus modifications:	
refine, potential modification mass:	Oxidation@M, Oxidation@W, Deamidated@N, Deamidated@Q
refine, potential modification mass 1:	Dioxidation@M, Dioxidation@W
refine, potential modification mass 2:	
refine, potential modification motif:	
refine, potential modification motif 1:	
refine, potential modification motif 2:	
refine, saps:	yes
refine, spectrum synthesis:	yes
refine, unanticipated cleavage:	yes
refine, use annotations:	yes
refine, use potential modifications for full refinement:	no
residue, modification mass:	Carbamidomethyl@C, Label:+6 Da@K, Label:+6 Da@R
residue, modification mass 1:	
residue, potential modification mass:	Oxidation@M, Phospho@S, Phospho@T, Phospho@Y
residue, potential modification motif:	
scoring, b ions:	yes
scoring, include reverse:	no
scoring, maximum missed cleavage sites:	1
scoring, minimum ion count:	4
scoring, y ions:	yes
spectrum, dynamic range:	100.0
spectrum, fragment mass type:	monoisotopic
spectrum, fragment monoisotopic mass error:	0.4
spectrum, fragment monoisotopic mass error units:	Daltons
spectrum, maximum parent charge:	4
spectrum, minimum fragment mz:	150.0
spectrum, minimum parent m+h:	500.0
spectrum, minimum peaks:	15
spectrum, parent monoisotopic mass error minus:	10
spectrum, parent monoisotopic mass error plus:	10
spectrum, parent monoisotopic mass error units:	ppm
spectrum, parent monoisotopic mass isotope error:	yes
spectrum, path:	C:\temp\CGItemp33452
spectrum, threads:	7
spectrum, total peaks:	50
spectrum, use contrast angle:	no
spectrum, use noise suppression:	no

Sample & project information:

Parameter	Value
BRENDA cell culture:	none

GO subcellular: none
 add: yes
 anonymous: no
 email:
 institution:
 name:
 project:
 project comment:
 store trace: yes

Analytical results:

Parameter	Value
list path, mods source #1:	../mods/crap_mod.xml
list path, mods source #2:	../mods/mouse_mod.xml
list path, saps source #1:	../saps/mouse_saps.xml
list path, sequence source #1:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.1.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #10:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.10.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #11:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.11.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #12:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.12.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #13:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.13.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #14:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.14.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #15:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.15.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #16:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.16.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #17:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.17.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #18:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.18.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #19:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.19.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #2:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.2.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #20:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.MT.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #21:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.other.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #22:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.X.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #23:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.Y.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #24:	../fasta/crap.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #3:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.3.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #4:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.4.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #5:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.5.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #6:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.6.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #7:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.7.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #8:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.8.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source #9:	../fasta/mouse/mouse_e.9.fasta.pro
list path, sequence source description #1:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 1
list path, sequence source description #10:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 10
list path, sequence source description #11:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 11
list path, sequence source description #12:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 12
list path, sequence source description #13:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 13
list path, sequence source description #14:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 14
list path, sequence source description #15:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 15
list path, sequence source description #16:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 16
list path, sequence source description #17:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 17
list path, sequence source description #18:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 18
list path, sequence source description #19:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 19
list path, sequence source description #2:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 2
list path, sequence source description #20:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr MT
list path, sequence source description #21:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 other
list path, sequence source description #22:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr X
list path, sequence source description #23:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr Y
list path, sequence source description #24:	GPM cRAP 2012.01.01
list path, sequence source description #3:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 3
list path, sequence source description #4:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 4
list path, sequence source description #5:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 5
list path, sequence source description #6:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 6
list path, sequence source description #7:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 7
list path, sequence source description #8:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 8
list path, sequence source description #9:	ENSEMBL NCBIM37.64 chr 9
modelling, estimated false positives:	81
modelling, total peptides used:	1111516490
modelling, total proteins used:	55913
modelling, total spectra assigned:	8989
modelling, total spectra used:	80084
modelling, total unique assigned:	2500
process, start time:	2018:03:14:12:31:30
process, version:	x! tandem CYCLONE (2011.05.01.1)
quality values:	2845 1565 990 736 733 640 607 563 540 489 460 401 342 331 306 253 237 200 194 162
refining, # input models:	855
refining, # input spectra:	73720
refining, # partial cleavage:	855
refining, # point mutations:	0
refining, # potential C-terminii:	0
refining, # potential N-terminii:	0
refining, # unanticipated cleavage:	289
timing, initial modelling total (sec):	289.32
timing, initial modelling/spectrum (sec):	0.0036
timing, load sequence models (sec):	0.38
timing, refinement/spectrum (sec):	0.0078

